

LASER SURFACE TREATMENT OF AL-SI ALLOYS AND AL-SI/SiC_p COMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

Over the last decades, the demand for light-weight materials with excellent mechanical properties, in automotive and aerospace industries, has attracted interest over Al-Si alloys and their corresponding metal matrix composites (PMMCs) [1, 2].

Low density, excellent castability, weldability, corrosion resistance and good tensile and fatigue properties as well as improved stiffness and high temperature properties and reduced coefficient of thermal expansion make Al-Si alloys suitable for many applications. The mechanical properties of Al-Si alloys can be greatly altered by changing the microstructure of the primary α -Al and the eutectic phase, which can be controlled by the solidification process. The general microstructure of a hypoeutectic Al-Si alloy consists of a dendritic primary α -Al solid solution, surrounded by eutectic regions along with intermetallic compounds. Commercial Al-Si alloys contain significant amounts of Fe and Mn as well as other elements that form brittle iron-rich intermetallics [3, 4].

Al-based composites reinforced with hard ceramic particulates like silicon carbide have become reference materials because of their low weight, strength, low thermal expansion coefficient and sufficiently high wear resistance [1]. Aluminium provides lightness and good corrosion performance, whereas silicon carbide improves mechanical properties rising the yield strength, hardness, and consequently, wear and abrasion resistance [5]. However, aluminium matrix composites exhibit poorer corrosion and wear resistance than expected because of the presence of coarse intermetallic phases in their surface, heterogeneous interfaces between matrix and reinforcement, and porosity [6].

Processing Al-Si/SiC_p composites has some difficulties related to the interaction between the matrix and the reinforcement. At high interaction temperatures, direct reaction between SiC and Al occurs to form hexagonal platelet-shaped Al₄C₃ crystals and free Si. The interfacial reaction has undesirable effects on the overall composites properties since Al₄C₃ is brittle and hygroscopic [7].

To achieve superior mechanical properties in Al-Si/SiC_p composites, it is essential to form adequate interfaces. To determine the local mechanical properties of the composite, it is necessary to develop experimental methodologies suitable for high heterogeneous regions and low scales. The capabilities of the Nanoindentation technique can be used for accurate measurement of interfacial mechanical properties on the nanometric scale in composites. Applied forces are in the mN range and penetration depths of several nanometres are used [8]. The Oliver-Pharr method is the most common method for establishing the projected contact area and predicting the elastic modulus used in commercial indentation instruments [9].

Surface modification treatments in Al-Si alloys and Al-Si/SiC_p composites become relevant considering the susceptibility of these materials to local pitting corrosion attack in chlorinated environments. Although aluminium is an extremely reactive metal, usually displays good corrosion resistance in aqueous solution due to the formation a passive alumina film. However, the presence of the SiC_p reinforcement could favour the formation of galvanic couples, moreover, the presence of SiC reinforcements could enhance the precipitation of detrimental intermetallics, therefore increase the number of pit nucleation sites in the composite material [10, 11].

Traditional surface treatments consist of depositing coatings over substrates. Hence, other routes emerge for microstructural modification surface treatments based on high energy sources such as ion beams, electron beams or laser light sources. Advantages of laser material processing are reasonable low cost, focusing on specific areas or geometrically complex surface treatment. Currently available laser systems are versatile elements which are used for cutting, welding and treatment for all materials, whether ceramics, polymers, metals or composites. Among the different laser source available CO₂, Nd:YAG and High Power Diode Laser (HPDL), HPDL are particularly suitable for surface treatments because they have a typical rectangular beam with top-hat profile in one direction and a Gaussian-like profile in the other direction. HPDL beams are also characterized by a relatively short wavelength (800-940 nm), which facilitates good transfer efficiency of the laser energy to most substrates, compactness, overall energy efficiency, lifetime and running cost [2, 5, 12].

Laser surface melting (LSM) is a well established technology applied to many materials for hardening, reducing porosity and increasing corrosion resistance. LSM using HPDL is a versatile and promising technology that can be used to modify the surface properties of a material without affecting its bulk property [6, 13]. The modifying in the surface properties of the material is due to rapid melting followed by rapid solidification. The intimate contact between the melt and the solid substrate causes a very fast heat extraction during solidification resulting in very high cooling rates of the order of 10⁵ to 10⁸ K/s. The high cooling rates to which this surface layer is submitted results in the formation of different microstructures from bulk metal leading to improved surface properties. Materials processed via rapid solidification tend to show advantages of refined microstructure, reduced microsegregation, extensive solid solubility and formation of metastable phases. Laser parameters such as laser power density, interaction time and scan speed affect on solidification behaviour and thus the microstructure of melted zone can be changed [14,15]. Recent studies have shown that total melting of the surface is not necessary to obtain improvements in mechanical properties. This process called Selective Laser Surface Melting

(SLSM) allows the melting of one phase of the alloy without altering the other phases of the material [16].

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of LSM and SLSM on Al-Si alloys, A356 y A380, and an Al-Si/SiCp composite, with a particular focus on the changes of the microstructure and hardness caused by the laser treatment. Excessive melting of the SiCp in the surface of the composite is to be avoided, so any possible deterioration of the mechanical properties and any excessive interfacial reaction can be prevented. Moreover, optimization of HPDL parameters was also evaluated to achieve the best treated material response.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1 Test Materials

Laser surface treatment has been applied to A356 and A380 alloys, and to A356 composite reinforced with 10% SiC particles. Substrates compositions are shown in Table 1. Al-Si/SiCp composite has been fabricated by stir casting process, with a SiCp average size of 15,3 μm.

2.2 Laser surface treatments

The dimensions of tested samples were 30 × 30 × 3 mm³. To improve the absorptivity of the laser power, two different surface pretreatments were tested after grinding to 1200 grit grade: etching in hot 3-wt.% NaOH for 5 min for the A356 and 2 min for the A380 and the A356/SiC/10p, and blackened with graphite paint.

The laser surface treatment process is illustrated schematically in Fig. 1. A HPDL from Rofin-Dilas (DL13S) with a maximum power of 1300 W and an emission wavelength of 940 nm was used in this work. The laser head was placed on an ABB IRB 2400/16 robot and allowed controlling the laser scan speed and the distance between consecutive laser lines. The scan speed of the laser source used was in the range 60-75 mm/s, whereas laser power was in the range 390 – 420 W. The distance between consecutive scans was 1.55 mm, and the distance between the laser and the surface of the samples

was 7 mm. No shielding gas was used during the laser melting process. Table 2 summarizes the applied pretreatment, laser power and scan speed for each laser condition.

For comparative purposes, Input Net Energy (INE, in J/mm) was estimated for each condition as a function of laser power and scan speed according to Eq. (2):

$$\text{INE (J/mm)} = \frac{\text{Input Laser Power (W)}}{\text{Scan Speed (mm/s)}} \quad (2)$$

2.3 Microstructural characterization

Metallographic specimens were cut from their cross section normal to the laser scanning direction, polished using common metallographic procedures and etched by Keller's etchant (0.5 mL hydrofluoric acid, 1.5 mL hydrochloric acid, 2.5 mL nitric acid and 95.5 mL distilled water) for 10 – 15 s.

Microstructural changes induced by laser treatment were investigated by both optical (OM, Leica DMR) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi S-3400N). Quantitative materials composition was determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF). Semi-quantitative composition measurements were performed by electron backscattering (BSE, Hitachi S-3400N) and X-ray energy dispersion spectroscopy (EDS, XFlash 2010 Bruker).

2.4 Vickers Hardness and Nanoindentation tests

The specimens were polished to have mirror-like surface so that microhardness and nanoindentation tests can be performed. The tests were carried out on the studied materials before and after the laser surface treatment. The microhardness of the cross sections of treated samples was measured over the laser melting depth direction using a Vickers Buehler Micromet 2100 micro-hardness tester with a load of 100 mN applied for 15 s. The microhardness values shown are the average of ten measurements for each condition.

Local mechanical properties of laser melted specimens were evaluated from the penetration force-displacement curves obtained by nanoindentation tests conducted in load control using a Nanoindenter XP (MTS) with a Berkovich

diamond indenter. Hardness distributions were determined by means of matrices of 100 tests (10×10), with a distance of 20 μm between marks, on cross samples sections with a maximum load of 5 mN applied at once. During nanoindentation tests the threshold for thermal drift was set to be less than 0.05 nm/s before experiments commenced. The indentation hardness, H, is estimated from the load-displacement curve using the Oliver and Pharr method for a Berkovich indenter. H is found from the Eq. (3) given as

$$H = \frac{P_{\max}}{A_p} \quad (3)$$

where P_{\max} is the maximum load and A_p is the projected area of the contact at that load between the indenter and the specimen and is determined from the load-displacement curve.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Microstructural characterization

3.1.1 Microstructures prior laser treatment

The microstructures of the base Al-Si alloys, A380 and A356, before the laser surface treatment are shown in Figure 2 and 3, respectively. Both alloys exhibited a typical hypoeutectic solidification structure of cast alloys, where the main phases are large primary α -Al dendrites (light gray), eutectic silicon (dark gray) between dendrite arms and intermetallic compounds (lighter gray).

The A380 microstructure (Fig. 2 a, b) basically consists of α -Al matrix, eutectic silicon and intermetallic phases. Eutectic Si exhibits platelet morphologies which appear as needles in section. Several intermetallic compounds are present in the A380 alloy showed in the EDS mappings of Figure 2 c and d. Regarding the Fe-rich phases in A380 alloy, the most common Fe-intermetallics are present. A380 alloy contains α -Al₃FeSi needles (Fig. 2 c) along with the dendritic phase α -Al(Fe,Mn,Cr)Si (Fig. 2 d). The Chinese script phase appears from α -Al₃FeSi phase when Cr is present [17]. Also there are Cu-rich phases with different morphologies named Al₂Cu which tend to be associated to the α -Al₃FeSi compounds.

In the A356 microstructure (Fig. 3 a, b) homogeneously distributed in grain boundary eutectic Si crystals are rounded as a result of Sr modification. The Fe-rich phase in A356 alloy is the $\text{-Al}_5\text{FeSi}$ intermetallic compound, which appear as needles or platelets in the microstructure. $\text{-Al}_5\text{FeSi}$ compound is known to be hard, brittle and presents low adhesion with the aluminium matrix. EDS mapping (Fig. 3 c, d) of the A356 alloy displays the morphologies and distributions of the eutectic silicon and the Fe-rich intermetallic phases.

Figure 4 shows the A356/SiC/10p composite microstructure which is formed by -Al dendrites, geometrically-shaped silicon carbide particles, eutectic silicon and Fe-rich precipitates. SiC particles are homogeneously distributed in the bulk composite material but tend to agglomerate at interdendritic spaces. In general, acceptable continuity between the aluminium matrix and the reinforcement is observed which may suggest that there is good wetting between the SiCp and the metal matrix, which also indicates a satisfactory bonding, though some discontinuities are observed in the interfaces Al-SiCp, especially when particle clustering is detected. Fe-rich intermetallic compounds in the composite are $\text{-Al}_5\text{FeSi}$ needles, coarse polyhedral -Al(Fe,Mn,Cr)Si and AlFeSiMgNi . Typical casting defects appear in the A356/SiC/10p composite such as micro-segregations and porosity that can favour the localised corrosion process [1].

3.1.2 Microstructural evolution after laser treatment. Laser parameters optimization

Laser surface treatment applied to A380, A356 alloys and to an A356/SiC/10p composite gives place to different microstructures depending of the treatment conditions. Transverse sections of the samples perpendicular to the laser beam movement show the contrast between the refined microstructure of the resolidified region close to the surface and the coarse dendritic structure typical of the unmelted substrate located at higher depth. In all cross-sections of the treated samples, the structure from the surface to the base material could be divided into three zones: the remelting zone (within this region depending on laser operating conditions, both LSM and SLSM could be present at high energy supplies,

or just SLSM at low energy supplies), the heat laser-affected zone and the base material.

Figure 5 displays the microstructures of the A380 alloy after laser treatment for two different operating conditions: at 4.5 J/mm (Fig. 5 a, b and c) and at 6.8 J/mm (Fig. 5 d, e and f). After analysing the microstructures of every treated sample, it is possible to have an understanding of the relation between the energy applied during the laser process and the treatment performed. When the laser input net energies are in the range of 4.3 – 4.5 J/mm for A380 alloy, SLSM of the microstructural constituents occurs; however, at lower energy densities no modification of the surfaces is observed. Conversely, when high laser input energies are applied, in the range of 5.4 – 5.6 J/mm for A380 alloy, the whole surface of the alloy is melted and LSM of the Al-Si alloy is carried out. The resulting microstructure of the A380 alloy after SLSM treatment (Fig. 5 a) exhibits two clearly distinguished zones, the remelting zone near to the surface and the base material located at higher depth (between them no heat laser-affected zone was detected apparently). Within the remelting zone two different constituents are observed, the eutectic phase which appears strongly altered after laser treatment and the primary -Al which seems to be unaffected; this behaviour suggests that at the employed value of the energy supply only allows the fusion of the phase with lower melting temperature. The remelted eutectic phase exhibits a refined morphology where the primary phase exhibits a greatly reduced dendritic size and the eutectic Si forms a fine network between the small dendrites. The unmelted primary -Al appears rounder than before to the laser treatment and some intermetallic compounds appear unmolten within the Al-Si phase.

After LSM is performed on the A380 alloy, its microstructure (Fig. 5 d) exhibits three clearly distinguished zones: the remelted zone near to the surface where both process, LSM and SLSM have taken place, and at higher depth the base material situated below. Near to the surface the microstructure shows a homogeneous and refined microstructure in which all constituents present before the treatment seems to be resolidified. In this continuous shallow remelted layer is where LSM is performed, whereas below it, a less uniform

microstructure with different constituents is observed, where SLSM treatment has occurred. In the LSM zone all constituents present before laser treatment seems to be affected by the treatment, resulting in the dissolution of the precipitates and the refining of the microstructure. In the SLSM zone the same features observed in the samples treated at lower input energies are observed, the primary α -Al phase appears globulized and the Al-Si phase is strongly refined. Below them no significant changes in the microstructure are detected.

Similar observations could be made for the treated A356 alloy. When the laser input net energies are in the range of 6.6 – 6.8 J/mm, SLSM is performed; on the contrary, when high laser input energies are in the range of 6.8 – 7.0 J/mm LSM takes place. The Figure 6 shows the microstructure of the A356 alloy after laser treatment at 6.8 J/mm (Fig. 6 a, b and c) and at 7.0 J/mm (Fig. 6 d, e and f). The SLSM treatment applied to an A356 aluminium alloy (Fig. 6 a) results in the partial fusion of the constituents of the alloy; it is observed from the figure that in a fine layer in the surface of the alloy has been modified by the process. In the resolidified layer it is possible to see that the eutectic phase has been changed, whereas the α -Al phase seems to be unaffected. The eutectic phase has become a fine network of eutectic silicon with little dendrites of phase α -Al, while the primary phase presents rounded morphologies, as it happened in the treatment of the A380 alloy. The main difference observed between the two alloys treated at SLSM conditions is the presence of undissolved precipitates within the remelted Al-Si eutectic phase. From the Figure 7, it is observed that in the SLSM treated A380 alloy (Fig. 7 b) unmelted intermetallic compounds are present in the resolidified phase, but they are not observed for the A356 alloy (Fig. 7 a), which is possible to see that in the compositional EDS mappings of the treated samples (Fig. 5 b c and 6 b c). It is also seen that in the resolidified Al-Si branches of the A356 alloy little porosity is still present, while in the A380 porosity seems to be avoided by the laser treatment.

The LSM of the A356 alloy (Fig. 6 d) originates the formation of the same zones in the microstructure of the alloy. Firstly, near to the surface the total fusion occurs and it is observed in the figure that a homogeneous layer is formed where no precipitates

or porosity is detected. In that layer, where LSM treatment has been performed, a high grade of refinement is achieved regarding the smaller dendrite size observed. Comparing both LSM zones of the treated alloys (Fig. 8) it is observed that the refined microstructures exhibits initial cellular growth from the bottom of the molten pool followed by a dendritic microstructure near to the surface as a result of the different cooling rates in both zones. In the A356 alloy (Fig. 8 a) the dendritic microstructure near to the surface seems to be wider which could be due to the faster heat elimination through the untreated material in the A356 alloy regarding the A380. Beneath the LSM zone, the SLSM zone appears and in which only the Al-Si eutectic branches have been changed by the treatment, while the primary phase appears globulized. Some unmelted particles of eutectic silicon are observed in the last portion of the resolidified branches of the eutectic phase (Fig. 6 f). Finally no significant changes are detected in the heat laser-affected zone.

Applying the laser surface treatment to the A356/SiC_{10p} composite again different microstructures are generated as a function of the employed laser operating parameters. At low input net energies, in the range of 6.6 – 6.8 J/mm (Fig. 9 a, b, c) development of both treatments happens which is seen in the Figure 9: LSM over the whole treated surface in shallow zones and SLSM happens at higher depths. For higher input net energies, i.e. 6.9 J/mm, laser surface melting occurs but excessive melting of the material happens resulting in the appearance of pores with different morphologies (Fig. 9 d, e, f).

As seen in Figure 9 a, at low depths from the surface when total melting of the composite is developed a high grade of homogenization is achieved and the resulting microstructures show special features: the formation of a refined microstructure where a high reduction of the dendritic size of the primary α -Al takes place; Si is rejected to the interdendritic spaces where forms a fine network; most intermetallic compounds are dissolved, although some coarse polyhedral α -Al(Fe,Mn,Cr)Si are still present and they exhibit fractures (Fig. 10 a); SiC_p reinforcement displays better contact with the aluminium matrix since Al-SiC_p interfaces exhibit a high grade of continuity; SiC_p shows a improved

distribution within the interdendritic places; casting defects as shrinkage porosity or evident segregations are removed, however some voids are present between particles, this happens because prior to laser treatment the inner part of SiCp clusters were not wetted by the aluminium matrix (Fig. 10 b). At higher depths from the surface when SLSM is performed total melting of the constituents situated at interdendritic spaces occurs while primary α -Al appear unaffected. This treatment allows the formation of globulized α -Al and similar behaviour with Al-Si alloys occurs with the refinement of the Al-Si branches. Within the homogenised branches of Al-Si eutectic SiCp appear well integrated and better distributed. In general, intermetallic compounds are dissolved. However, employing higher energy densities over the composite surface as it is seen in Figure 9 d results in the appearance of large rounded and needle-like pores in the resolidified zone which is expected to have detrimental effects over the mechanical properties of the composite.

Finally, the analysis of the laser operates conditions used in the present study demonstrates that high laser input energies along with low laser scan speeds give rise to the fusion of the widest remelted layers in the surface of the treated materials. The enlargement of the molten pool is a result of an increase in the interaction time between the laser beam and the sample. On the contrary, using higher scan speeds for the same power allows the reduction of the interaction time and therefore a rising of the cooling rate leading to lower remelted depths.

3.2 Mechanical characterization

3.2.1 Microhardness tests

Fig. 11 displays the Vickers micro-Hardness of the treated materials for both conditions SLSM (Fig. 11 a, c, e) and LSM (Fig. 11 b, d, f, g). In general, laser surface treatment of Al-Si alloys and Al/SiCp composites increased the hardness of the material surfaces for all evaluated conditions and it decreases with depth. Measured micro-hardness of the starting materials are $93,5 \pm 14,8$ for the A356-T6, $62,3 \pm 17,8$ for the as-cast A380 and $94,3 \pm 5,3$ in the A356/10%SiC composite. Elevated hardening is achieved in the treated materials regarding the starting hardness of the materials, specifically 25 %

for A356, 50 % for A380 alloy and 50 % in the composite.

Regarding the results showed on Figure 11, SLSM provides the highest micro-hardness values at the top of the treated surfaces compared with the LSM treatment. In general, within the remelted zone in LSM conditions the highest hardening occurs at the lowest depths as a result of the highest microstructure refinement. At higher depths for both treatments, when only the Al-Si phase is remelted a high grade of hardening is achieved on the resolidified Al-Si branches, maybe due to refined phase and the presence of unmolten precipitates. On the contrary, little hardening occurs in the unmolten α -Al dendrites, they exhibit similar hardness to the untreated materials. Finally, no hardening is observed on the heat laser-affected zone, in fact micro-hardness values are in general lower than the ones of the starting materials, maybe due to the result of the heat conduction from the molten zone.

Hardness evolution as a function of laser parameters demonstrates that as the depth of the melted layer, hardness is dependent on energy supply. Higher laser power for the same scan velocities implies longer depths of the molten pool and therefore a higher hardness variation within the depth take place. Higher scan speeds for the same power implies higher cooling rates and a result higher hardening is expected.

3.2.2 Nanoindentation tests

Hardness nanoindentation mappings and compositional EDS mappings of each treated material are collected on Figure 12. Hardness mappings show that the highest values corresponding to the “hot” colours of the hardness mappings, while the “cooler” colours correspond to the softest values. Nanoindentation tests are calculated over cross-sections of the samples and from them, average hardness values of each phase are calculated and together in Table 3.

In general, hardness values obtained by nanoindentation show similar tendencies than the micro-hardness calculated previously. Both mappings displayed on Fig. 12 exhibit good matches between them, resolidified zones have the highest

hardness value and SiC_p and unmolten intermetallic compounds reach the highest values of local hardness.

Hardness distribution in the resolidified A380 alloy (Fig. 12 a) along with the average values shown in Table 3 demonstrate the hardening effect of the treatment in both conditions SLSM and LSM. When LSM is performed the whole surface is hardened, however in the SLSM treatment just the eutectic phase presents an increase in the measured hardness. In the A356 alloy (Fig. 12 b) the hardening effect of the treatment is lower for both conditions. In the laser treatment of the composite (Fig. 12 c), little hardening effect is observed in the LSM condition regarding the untreated material. However, when SLSM is developed a great hardening effect is achieved in the resolidified branches of the eutectic phase, whereas the primary one remains with the same hardness than before the treatment. Figure 13 a displays a nanoindentation matrix performed over the SLSM treated surface of the processed composite and the Figure 13 b shows the load-displacement curves of the tests made on the resolidified eutectic phase and the unmolten primary one, along with the curve of the SiC_p particles.

4. Discussion

Regarding the microstructures of the Al-Si base alloys before laser treatment, as hypoeutectic alloys, solidification firstly begins with growth of α -Al primary phase while Al-Si eutectic is driven by the solidification forefront to the interdendritic spaces where solidifies last. Mechanical properties of Al-Si casting alloys depend not only on their chemical compositions but also on their microstructures such as the morphologies of α -Al phase or the size, shape and distribution of the brittle eutectic silicon phase [3, 18]. When primary α -Al phase is small, regular and globular, the mechanical properties of alloy should be improved [19]. When eutectic silicon particles are elongated frequently generate fracture as they are the main sources of stress concentration [20]. As known, modification could alter the growth of the eutectic silicon to produce an irregular fibrous form rather than the usual acicular structure. The coarser eutectic Si phase greatly deteriorates the strength and elongation of A356 alloy. The Sr

modification treatment of Al-Si alloy could lead to considerable improvements in properties and high cooling speed has remarkable effects on the improvement of the process of strontium metamorphism [18].

Concerning the microstructures of the Al-Si alloys after laser treatment, as laser treatment imposes a great energy density on the surface of the materials, and the matrix of the aluminium alloy has high heat conduction, a very steep temperature gradient would be produced on the surface of the melted metal. As a result, the laser melting treatment causes the surface of the alloy to produce very high undercooling and a very fast growth rate. For that reason, laser treatment causes the primary α -Al and Al-Si eutectic to be finer. As a result of the rapid solidification of the laser-melted zone, finer grains were formed in the surface and columnar crystals were produced along the heat-flow direction near to the base metal [21].

SLSM of A356 and A380 Al-Si alloys gives rise to the formation of a fine Si network situated at interdendritic spaces as a result of the rapid melting followed of rapid solidification, whereas the primary α -Al remain unaffected within the remelted zone. At low laser input energies during melting, when the temperature at the surface of the sample is lightly above 577 °C (eutectic transformation temperature) only the Al-Si eutectic phase is quickly molten and resolidified. This behaviour originates a microstructure partially homogenised where the α -Al appears globulized and between dendrites a high refined microstructure is achieved. Globulization of the α -Al is produced because of the large stress effect produced by the fast solidification and large shrinkage of laser melting [21].

When LSM is performed on the surface of A356 and A380 Al-Si alloys a total melting of every constituent present before treatment takes place. The application of high laser input energies allows the surface to reach high temperatures during melting, specifically when melting temperatures are above 660 °C all the phases are molten. High cooling rates of the melt after LSM resulting in the formation of a fine and homogeneous microstructure with a great reduction of the dendrite size of the α -Al phase and Si at interdendritic zones. Therefore, a supersaturated α -Al phase is formed because laser

treatment causes a much large solubility of the silicon atom compared to the maximum solid solubility under equilibrium conditions (1.65 %) as a result of the fast solidifying process [21]. In A356 the enrichment of the primary phase is silicon atoms, whereas in A380 alloy is in copper too. In general, a few intermetallic compounds appear undissolved within the total melting zone for both alloys which indicates a high grade of homogenization.

Laser treatment applied to Al/SiCp composites allows for one hand a high refinement of the microstructure, better bonding and distribution of the reinforcement and elimination of porosities leading to a great improvement of mechanical properties of the composite; on the other hand, the suppression of the most brittle phases situated at interdendritic spaces, which are the critical zones of the composite where SiCp tends to agglomerate, along with the control of the onset of pores and segregations results in an important progress in corrosion properties of the composite.

Hardening of a thin surface layer in Al-Si alloys may be due to fine distribution of α -Al dendrites in the oversaturated solid solution, dissolution/better distribution of brittle intermetallic compounds [22] and may also be the result of the precipitation of Si crystals from the supersaturated solutions after solidification [21]. In the case of Al/SiCp composites the hardening is due to the better integration and distribution of SiCp, along with the lack of porosity.

Average values of nanoindentation hardness for the whole remelted surface in the LSM treatment, and for the Al-Si resolidified branches and the primary unmolten α -Al in the SLSM treatment demonstrate that hardness values of resolidified microstructures in LSM are between the ones achieved in the SLSM treatment. SLSM treatment allows reaching the highest values of hardness in the Al-Si resolidified branches which indicates that it is a valid method for hardening the surface of the materials without altering the whole material. With regard to the unmolten α -Al in the SLSM treatment it is observed that little hardening is achieved for all treated samples which is a result of the oversaturation in Si atoms for the A356 and the composite and Si and Cu atoms for the A380 alloy, along with the stress that

is supported by the unmolten phase during solidification.

5. Conclusions

LSM and SLSM treatments have been successfully applied to Al-Si alloys and Al/SiCp composites and microstructures with a high grade of refinement and homogenization are achieved. Using moderate energy supplies it is possible to melt only the phase with lower melting point during the selective treatment, which means the refinement of the Al-Si phase while the primary α -Al remain unmolten, though displays some globulization. Selective treatment allows an improvement in mechanical properties as porosity and brittle zones are eliminated, and overall, because allows the highest hardenings in the resolidified branches. In composites, also an enhancement in SiCp bonding and distribution is reached. Just at the highest energy supplies the presence of Al_4C_3 is detected which indicates excessive melting and damage of the mechanical properties. Great hardenings are reached in all resolidified surfaces.

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Tables and Figures

Table 1. Chemical composition (wt.%) of used alloys and composites measured by XRF.

Material	Elements (wt.%)						Al
	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Zn	
A356	9.295	0.117	0.003	0.001	0.310	0.003	Rest
A380	9.351	0.625	2.248	0.126	0.176	0.908	Rest
A356/SiC _{10p}	16.88	0.739	0.004	0.012	0.794	0.005	Rest

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of LSM and SLSM process.

Table 2. Input net energies.

Material	INE (J/mm)									
A380	4,3 (p)	4,5 (p)	5,2 (p)	5,4 (p)	5,6 (p)	6,5 (p)	6,6 (p)	6,6 (s)	6,8 (p)	6,8 (s)
A356	5,2 (p)	5,4 (p)	5,6 (p)	6,5 (p)	6,6 (p)	6,8 (p)	6,9 (p)	7,0 (p)		
A356/SiC _{10p}	6,6 (p)	6,6 (s)	6,8 (p)	6,8 (s)	6,9 (p)	6,9 (s)				

Note: Pretreatment with graphite paint (p), hot NaOH etching (s).

Figure 2. Base alloy A380: a) SE micrograph, b) BSE micrograph, c) and d) EDS mappings.

Figure 3. Base alloys A356: a) SE micrograph, b) BSE micrograph, c) and d) EDS mappings.

Figure 4. A356/10%SiCp base materials: BSE and EDS analysis.

Figure 5: A380 treated with 405 W a, b, c) 90 mm/s and d, e, f) 60 mm/s

Figure 6: A356 treated with 60 mm/s and a,b,c) 405 W, d,e,f) 420 W.

Figure 7: a) SLSM A356 treated with 75 mm/s and 405 W; b) A380 treated with 90 mm/s and 405 W.

Figure 8: a) LSM A356 treated with 75 mm/s and 420 W; b) A380 treated with 60 mm/s and 398 W.

Figure 9: A356/10%SiC treated with 60 mm/s a,b,c) 405 W, d,e,f) 413 W.

Figure 10: a) LSM+SLSM A356/10%SiC treated with 60 mm/s and 398 W; b) LSM A356/10%SiC treated with 60 mm/s and 413 W.

Figure 11: a) A356 60 mm/s and 405 W, b) A356 60 mm/s and 420 W, c) A380 90 mm/s and 405 W, d) A380 60 mm/s and 420 W, e) A356/10%SiC 60 mm/s and 398 W and f) A356/10%SiC 60 mm/s and 405 W, g) A356/10%SiC 60 mm/s and 405 W (continued).

Table 3. Average values of nanoindentation hardness for each phase.

Material	Nanoindentation Hardness (GPa)		
	LSM	SLSM	
	-Al + Al-Si	-Al	Al-Si
A380	1,8 ± 0,4	1,2 ± 0,2	2,1 ± 0,7
A356	1,0 ± 0,1	0,8 ± 0,1	1,0 ± 0,1
A356/SiC/10p	1,3 ± 0,2	1,3 ± 0,1	2,2 ± 1,2

Figure 12: Hardness and compositional mappings: a) A356 60 mm/s and 405 W, b) A380 60 mm/s and 420 W, c) A356/10%SiC 60 mm/s and 405 W.

Figure 13: a) Nanoindentation imprints on A356/10%SiC treated at 60 mm/s and 405 W, b) Load-displacement curves of the main phases of A356/10%SiC after SLSM treatment.